
Open-Box Target for Extrinsic Calibration of LiDAR, Camera and Industrial Robot

Aquib Rashd

Robotics Department, Fraunhofer IWU
Chemnitz, Germany
Aquib.rashid@iwu.fraunhofer.de

Alexey Kolker

Faculty of Automation and Computer Engineering
Novosibirsk State Technical University
Russia

Wolfram Hardt

Department of Computer Engineering, TUC
Chemnitz, Germany

Mohamad Bdiwi

Robotics Department,
Fraunhofer IWU

Matthias Putz

Fraunhofer IWU
Chemnitz, Germany

Abstract—Low cost 3D LiDAR complement cameras in perception application for various industrial environments. Safe and efficient human robot collaboration requires easy and accurate extrinsic calibration of sensors with an industrial robot. This work presents an efficient and accurate method for extrinsic calibration between LiDAR, camera and a heavy-duty industrial robot. Open-box target mounted on robot enables parameter estimation by constraining sensor data to multiple planes, which constitute the target surface. The method enables eight correspondences between the sensors and the robot in each data sample. The method enables speedup in sensor setup and drastically reduces efforts required for data collection through automation. The results have been evaluated for simulated and real environment.

Keywords—Extrinsic-calibration; LiDAR; Camera; Industrial Robot, open-box, plane constraint

I. INTRODUCTION

Applications of low-cost 3D LiDAR in production industry for human robot collaboration is an emerging field. 360° horizontal field of view can help detect human entry as well as track worker inside the cell to increase flexibility and safety [1]. Fusion of 3D LiDAR and camera is being used for various robotic perception research to improve flexibility and efficiency [2, 3]. Multi-modal sensor fusion enables higher estimation of dynamic object detection. This enables collision avoidance with large heavy-duty robot (manipulator arm).

Extrinsic calibration; which is required for fusion; deals with estimating pose of one sensor with respect to other. Sparse LiDAR data of less than 16 channel makes the accuracy of these estimations challenging. Inaccurate estimations may lead to wrong shortest distance estimation between robot and human, which in turn may result to collision. Furthermore, in an agile production cell, sensor position may change often based on the process specifications. Thus, faster and accurate extrinsic calibration is of high importance.

The accuracy of calibration estimation depends on the quality and quantity of point correspondences. These properties are directly related to the sensor used, e.g. field of view and resolution of sensors. Furthermore, the method used to estimate the 3D-3D or 3D-2D point correspondences between sparse LiDAR and high-quality camera data. Although there exist various methods for LiDAR and camera calibration, the field of joint calibration of low-resolution 3D LiDAR, with camera and an industrial robot is an active field of research.

Available methods can be categorized into target-less [4-7] and target-based approaches [8-13]. The target-based approach can provide required accuracy and efficiency for stationary sensor setup. The available methods [8-13], however, are inefficient for the extrinsic calibration of low-resolution LiDAR with camera and industrial robot, with constraints on data collection within robot cell.

Calibration methods for low resolution LiDAR focus on filtering and fitting the sparse data for accurate estimations. Park et al. [10] emphasized on noise generated in LiDAR data from traditional checkerboard targets, and proposed using white triangle and diamond shaped planer targets with unbiased inlier ratio to improve plane constraints. Furthermore, by using virtual points in their 32-channel LiDAR data, the method enhanced the polygonal edge estimation, which in turn resulted in higher accuracy corner estimation. These corner positions acted as point correspondences between LiDAR and manually clicked image corner pixels. Dhall et al. [13], used similar diamond shaped target boards, as by [10], for extracting 3D point correspondences in a 16-channel LiDAR. This method, furthermore, used ArUco markers [14] to remove manual image correspondences selection. Pusztai et al. [11] proposed flexible method for extrinsic calibration by using ordinary boxes. The only constraint while collecting data is to have three perpendicular sides visible. The method proposed filters a 16-channel LiDAR data using box fitting and refinement methods. This results in extracting seven-point correspondences from each data sample.

Main limitations of these methods are: 1) They are implemented for higher resolution LiDAR, 2) they are focused for calibrating LiDAR camera only, thus, evoking additional effort for robot calibration and 3) the data collection is not constrained from a large occlusion-causing robot.

This work proposes novel open-box target-based calibration method, which simultaneously estimates calibration parameters between LiDAR, camera and robot. The open-box structure exploits extra-planner surfaces in the data collection process, compared to state of art, which not only helps in the filtering process for more quality data, but also ensure maximum collection of spare LiDAR data. The method efficiently extracts double number of correspondences from a single LiDAR scan than Park et al. [10] and one-point correspondence more than Pusztai et al. [11]. Moreover, for each data sample, the robot correspondence in base coordinate system is also collected, which is not provided by the previous works.

The paper is organized in five sections. After introduction, Section II describes the proposed method. Section III describes experimental setup for synthetic and real-world experimental. Section IV discuss results and Section V gives conclusion and future steps of our approach.

II. PROPOSED METHOD

The work proposes a novel method for target-based efficient calibration of sensors and robot. Fig. 1 illustrates the open-box target designed and the general sensor setup used in this work. The target is used to collect data samples from LiDAR and Camera at defined positions.

Figure 1: Open-box target in front of LiDAR and Camera

The calibration board comprises of a main plane, P1, facing sensors and 4 side-planes P2-P5. Side-plane pairs are parallel and perpendicular to P1. The board is 1m in length in all sides, with depth of side boards being 0.3m. The size of the board is computed from the vertical field of view (θ_{LiDAR})

of LiDAR used and maximum distance at which the data sample is collected

$$B = 2 * \tan\left(\frac{\theta_L}{2}\right) * D \quad (1)$$

where B , represents diagonal length of the target board, θ_L represents vertical field of view of the LiDAR used and D is the maximum distance at which data samples are collected. For a robotic cell, this would be less than the twice overall range of the robot. The main constraint while collecting data is that all of the LiDAR channels should be captured on five planes, with majority points on main plane P1.

The coordinate axis of the board coincides with the coordinate axis of the tool center point (TCP), or the hand of the robot, with translation of 7.5cm in Z axis. The X and Y axis point towards the vertices of the box as shown in the Figure 1. The robot controller provides the TCP pose in robot base coordinate, which is used to determine the target corner positions in robot coordinate system.

Target board corner extraction from the sparse data is a challenging problem. Thus, focus has been placed on estimation the box vertices. Main aim is to determine the 1) Intrinsic camera matrix C along with transformation matrix $[R|t]$, if camera intrinsic are not given, 2) Extrinsic parameters of camera with respect to LiDAR, when camera intrinsic are available.

The proposed method is illustrated by the block diagram in Fig 2. The work assumes LiDAR scan lines l_i falling on inner or outer surface of the side-planes as same plane. This additional plane constraint helps to better estimate all of the eight corners. Furthermore, for automatic image corner extraction, ArUco markers have been placed on the planes, which further accelerates the calibration process, with known camera intrinsic. The method comprises of three main modules, on LiDAR processing, Camera processing and extrinsic calibration through PnP method.

A. LiDAR point cloud processing

Point cloud data is manually preprocessed to reduce the number of computations. The cropped point cloud comprises of the board with a part of robot manipulator. This data is fed to the automatic feature extraction module. This module performs a stage-wise filtering of input cropped point cloud. In the first phase, the main plane (P1), is extracted. RANSAC algorithm for plane filtering, with given parameters (1000 iterations, 30 neighboring set, 0.05m inlier tolerance) Plane model for main plane (P1) is determined. In the next phase, each of the rays on the target are clustered separately. Using *Kdtree*, the individual scan lines are clustered on the box are parsed to cluster the nearest neighbors. Iterating over all these scan lines, shortest distance between the points and the extracted plane is determined using general point to plane distance equation:

Figure 2: Block diagram of proposed method

$$Distance = \frac{ax_0+by_0+cz_0+d}{\sqrt{a^2+b^2+c^2}} \quad (2)$$

where, a, b, c, d are the parameters of plane equation and (x_0, y_0, z_0) represents the 3D point, from which we compute the distance.

In 3D corner extraction module, these distances are sorted and filtering, we obtain the end points of outer edges on the side-planes (P_{outer}). These points are then projected on the extracted main plane, to obtain the edge points on the main plane. The projection of a point P_{outer}^i on the plane, with normal vector given by (a, b, c) , and distance to the plane from (2), is given by:

$$P_{inner}^i = P_{outer}^i - Distance_i * (a, b, c) \quad (3)$$

where P_{inner}^i is projected point on edges of the main plane. The set of the points in P_{outer} and P_{inner} , are used for line fitting, which in turn determines the eight corners of the target box in LiDAR coordinate system. Fig 3, presents intermediate results of target box point cloud at different orientations. As illustrated, in some scenarios the edge points are not properly estimated or detected. However, it does not largely affect the results of the corner estimation. Furthermore, from each of the ray lines, mean is determined, by traversing through all the points in the line. This provides the middle point of the ray

Figure 3 Outer Edge Points

B. Camera processing

The module in camera processing deals with 2D pixel coordinate extraction from RGB image. Two separate processes are used for this target. The scenario where the camera intrinsic matrix is unknown, the target box corners are manually selected and refined by ORB[15] corner detector. This represents the first process when the system is calibrated.

Once the camera matrix is known, the corner positions estimation is automated using ArUco markers. The placement and relative measurement of marker on the plane is performed once. This, however, facilitates accurate corner measurements for future changes, which are often in agile process.

Marker processing provides us the rotation and translation matrices of camera in marker coordinate system. Marker M_i , shown in Figure 4, having null point at the center. The position of the points f , can be expressed in marker coordinate system as $(0, (\frac{x}{2}) + w_i)$, where x represents the size of the marker, and w_i represents the position of marker from the edge. Projection matrix from camera model is used to estimate position of corners in image coordinates. Then using projection matrix, this points is projected on the camera image.

C. PnP for Camera matrix estimation

The set of correspondences between the sets of point

Figure 4 ArUco Markers for automation

clouds and images data for different positions are given to PnP [18] algorithm followed by Lavenberg-Marquardt [19] optimization to extract intrinsic and extrinsic parameters between the LiDAR and camera. EPnP [20] is used to estimate extrinsic parameters of camera with respect to LiDAR for scenarios with known camera matrix,

III. EXPERIMENTS

A. Synthetic Setup

Blensor [17] has been used to setup a virtual scenario, with virtual camera and 32-channel virtual LiDAR. The extrinsic parameters estimated by the proposed method are compared with the ground truth to calculate translation error as suggested by Pusztai et al.[11]

B. Real Setup

The real setup comprises of Quanergy M8 LiDAR with 8 channels and Stereolabs ZED camera with full HD resolution. Only the left camera images are considered for the experimental evaluations. The sensors are placed as shown in the Figure 5. The calibration target is mounted on Kuka KR180 using an easy to use adapter.

8 positions are taken in a range of 3-5m from the sensor at different orientations, while maintaining the data input constraints of capturing almost all scan lines from LiDAR on the target board and 8-point visibility in RGB image. Open3D [16] has been used for point cloud processing data.

Figure 5 Real experimental Setup

IV. RESULTS

The amount of time required to collect data from LiDAR, camera and robot is reduced. Current results have been focused on estimating intrinsic and extrinsic calibration and future results would include joint optimizations in robot coordinate system. The evaluations are performed by taking specific number of target box positions at a time to estimate calibration parameters. These estimations are used to evaluate average reprojection error on remaining correspondence sets. The reprojection error as shown in Fig 6 converges after four target samples to six pixels. Future works will aim to further reduce this error.

The estimated calibration parameters are used to project LiDAR points on the corresponding RGB image, as shown in Figure 7, to perform the qualitative analysis on results.

Figure 6 Reprojection error on 7 data positions

Figure 7 LiDAR points projected with Extrinsic Parameters

Furthermore, the Blender camera intrinsic parameters are estimated to compute position of LiDAR, with ground truth about its position known. The robustness of the system to noise is evaluated against the state of art approaches as suggested by Pusztai [11]. Translation error is lower than Pusztai (represented as Box method) and Park (represented by Polygonal method) until gaussian noise of sigma 0.1, as shown in Figure 8

Figure 8 Translation error in simulation

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed work presents a calibration method to get efficient calibration estimation between eight channel LiDAR sensors and a camera. A novel target board, which exploits the plane feature extraction from sparse LiDAR data has been used to efficiently generate eight 3D-2D correspondences from each sample position. Stage wise filtering is used to improve the quality of position estimation of 3D corner from the LiDAR. Two target sample positions are sufficient for the intrinsic and extrinsic parameter estimation. The average reprojection error at four target samples is reduced to 6 pixels. The quality of the estimations would be further improved in future work. The method has been compared to the state of art algorithms for extrinsic calibration estimation in synthetic world. The proposed allows intuitive and faster calibration of sensors and robot. Furthermore, once intrinsic parameters are known, the extrinsic calibration estimation is fully automatic. Thus, enabling assembly or disassembly tasks [21] in Agile robotic cells.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work is supported by ICU project (ERA.NET RUS Plus, European Commission G.A. 609556).

REFERENCES

- [1] Associated Press in Berlin. "Robot kills worker at Volkswagen plant in Germany". <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2015/jul/02/robot-kills-worker-at-volkswagen-plant-in-germany>. Accessed: 2020-06-05.
- [2] M. Buehler, K. Iagnemma, and S. Singh. The 2005 darpa grand challenge:
- [3] Rashid, Aquib et. al. "Local and Global Sensors for Collision Avoidance." Multisensor Fusion and Integration (MFI), 2020
- [4] G. Pandey, J. R. McBride, S. Savarese, and R. M. Eustice, "Automatic targetless extrinsic calibration of a 3D LiDAR and camera by maximizing mutual information," in Proc. 26th AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell., 2012, pp. 2053–2059.
- [5] S. Bileschi, "Fully automatic calibration of LiDAR and video streams from a vehicle," in Proc. 2009 IEEE 12th Int. Conf. Comput. Vision Workshops, 2009, pp. 1457–1464.
- [6] Ravi, Radhika, et al. "Simultaneous system calibration of a multi-lidar multicamera mobile mapping platform." *IEEE Journal of selected topics in applied earth observations and remote sensing* 11.5 (2018): 1694-1714.
- [7] Jesse Levinson and Sebastian Thrun. Automatic online calibration of cameras and lasers. In *Robotics: Science and Systems IX*. Robotics: Science and Systems Foundation, June 24–28, 2013
- [8] Andreas Geiger, Frank Moosmann, Omer Car, and Bernhard Schuster. Automatic camera and range sensor calibration using a single shot. In *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2012, pages 3936–3943, Piscataway, NJ, 2012. IEEE
- [9] V. Fremont and P. Bonnifait, "Extrinsic calibration between a multi-layer LiDAR and a camera," in Proc. 2008 IEEE Int. Conf. Multisens. Fusion Integr. Intell. Syst., 2008, pp. 214–219
- [10] Yoonsu Park, Seokmin Yun, Chee Sun Won, Kyungeun Cho, KyhyunUm, and Sungdae Sim. Calibration between color camera and 3d lidar instruments with a polygonal planar board. *Sensors (Basel, Switzerland)*, 14(3):5333–5353, 2014
- [11] Pusztai, Zoltán, Iván Eichhardt, and Levente Hajder. "Accurate calibration of multi-lidar-multi-camera systems." *Sensors* 18.7 (2018): 2139.
- [12] Vefas, Martin, et al. "Calibration of rgb camera with velodyne lidar." (2014).
- [13] Dhall, Ankit, et al. "LiDAR-camera calibration using 3D-3D point correspondences." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1705.09785* (2017).
- [14] Garrido-Jurado, Sergio, et al. "Automatic generation and detection of highly reliable fiducial markers under occlusion." *Pattern Recognition* 47.6 (2014): 2280-2292.
- [15] Ethan Rublee, Vincent Rabaud, Kurt Konolige, and Gary Bradski. Orb: an efficient alternative to sift or surf. In *Computer Vision (ICCV)*, 2011 IEEE International Conference on, pages 2564–2571. IEEE, 2011.
- [16] Zhou, Qian-Yi, Jaesik Park, and Vladlen Koltun. "Open3D: A modern library for 3D data processing." *arXiv preprint arXiv:1801.09847* (2018).
- [17] Gschwandtner, Michael, et al. "BlenSor: Blender sensor simulation toolbox." *International Symposium on Visual Computing*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2011.
- [18] Zhang, Zhengyou. "A flexible new technique for camera calibration." *IEEE Transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence* 22.11 (2000): 1330-1334.
- [19] Moré, Jorge J. "The Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm: implementation and theory." *Numerical analysis*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1978. 105-116.
- [20] Lepetit, Vincent, Francesc Moreno-Noguer, and Pascal Fua. "EpnP: An accurate o(n) solution to the pnp problem." *International journal of computer vision* 81.2 (2009): 155.
- [21] Bdiwi, Mohamad, Aquib Rashid, and Matthias Putz. "Autonomous disassembly of electric vehicle motors based on robot cognition." *2016 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2016.